

Gemini North Returns to Operations Following the Repair of Its Primary Mirror

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Figure 8: Coated Gemini North primary mirror with the Gemini/NOIRLab coating and shutdown team Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

Figure 1: GN M1 Top & Side View of M1 Damage (measurements in mm). M1 was impacted at two locations by the earthquake restraint (Damage Area #1) and a nearby bolt (Damage Area #2). Damage Area #1 was a roughly triangle-shaped chip extending ~20 cm along the full vertical edge of the mirror and ~30 cm between lateral pads 9 and 10. Damage Area #2 was a smaller chip a few cm in diameter at the underside (non-reflective) of the mirror. Credit: Safran-Reosc

Figure 2: Damaged areas of the glass and Lateral Pads 9 (left) and 10 (right). The location of the damage close to a lateral actuator pad (L10), and the potential for additional undetected cracks behind the pad meant that removal and replacement of L10 would need to be performed as part of the repairs. Credit: Safran-Reosc

On the evening of 02 June 2023, the Gemini North telescope restarted operations for the first time since October 2022. The telescope performed beautifully after an almost eight-month hiatus, with a newly repaired and coated primary mirror achieving its full performance. The Gemini North science

Figure 3: Removal of the Pad L10 from GN M1 by Jean-Benoît de Vanssay. Credit: Safran-Reosc

operations team kicked off the first science observations with a staff-led Director's Discretionary program to observe SN2023ixf in the nearby galaxy M101.

This successful outcome followed a challenging and intense program by NOIRLab to recover from the damage to the primary mirror incurred on 20 October 2022 during preparations to recoat the mirror with its reflective silver layer. While lowering the M1 onto the washcart used to hold the mirror during stripping of the old coating, the mirror impacted an earthquake restraint on the side of the cart. Fortunately, there were no injuries associated with the incident, and the damage was limited to two chips on the outer edge of the mirror, in a section that is outside the area collecting light for observations.

Although the damage to M1 was limited, careful planning for the repairs was needed to ensure that the damage would not propagate or cause

additional issues with the telescope performance. The immediate cause of the accident was human error, due to a radio communications mishap between the crane operator and the team lowering the mirror. However, there were multiple factors contributing to the event. These included insufficient management and safety oversight, unclear mirror handling procedures at the point of the incident, perceived time pressure, and the long interval between M1 coatings. Immediately following the

Figure 4: Thierry Lagrange grinding of Damage Area #1. Credit: Safran-Reosc

accident, it was necessary to take the needed time to understand the root causes and address them before the mirror was handled again.

The Gemini North telescope undergoes regular maintenance work to maintain the performance of its complex systems. Its primary mirror is a 8.1m diameter monolithic piece of ultra-low expansion glass, actively controlled by a series of actuators and coated with silver to

Figure 5: NOIRLab GN M1 team members Gary Pozculp, Tom Schneider, and Heather Carr prepare witness samples to test the L10 epoxy application and bonding to ULE glass block. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/Katie Smither*

provide high reflectivity at optical-infrared (OIR) wavelengths. While the mirror is regularly cleaned, the reflective coating degrades over time and must be stripped off and reapplied to maintain the telescope's optimal light-collecting power. This is a significant, high-risk activity that requires removing the 25-ton mirror from its mounting on the telescope structure and lowering it several floors to the coating area. The mirror is stripped of its old coating and then moved into the coating chamber for application of the new coating. Finally, the primary mirror is raised up to the telescope level, reconnected to the mirror cell, and reinstalled onto the telescope. In normal times, this activity is performed every five years, with the other mirrors (secondary mirror,

science fold) coated in off-years in between.

The last time the Gemini North primary mirror (GN M1) was coated was in 2014, a long hiatus due to a series of unplanned events. This work was originally planned for July 2019, which ended up coinciding with the Thirty Meter Telescope protests on the Maunakea access road. Given the challenges with access to the telescope, Gemini management decided to defer the primary mirror coating until the summer of 2020. In 2020, NOIRLab halted all nighttime operations in response to the global COVID-19 pandemic. While Gemini North resumed observations in May 2020, in-person work at the telescope was limited in order to minimize the potential COVID exposure of critical staff. In 2021, we successfully recoated the smaller, easier to handle Gemini North secondary mirror, gaining 8% improvement in overall telescope throughput. With

Figure 6: NOIRLab M1 repair team members placing the new L10 lateral pad into position on the Gemini North primary mirror. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/Katie Smither*

COVID-19 in decline and the majority of staff vaccinated, we planned a six-week shutdown of the Gemini North telescope to include the GN M1 coating to start in October 2022. The GN M1 incident occurred ten days into the shutdown, following the removal of the primary mirror from the telescope support structure and transport of the mirror to the pier support level.

The months-long effort to recover from the incident, repair the mirror, and

Figure 7: M1 after repairs and installation of new L10 pad. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/Katie Smither*

Figure 8: GMOS imaging observations of the M101 supernova 2023ixf taken 02–05 June 2–5 2023. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Miller/M. Rodriguez/M. Zamani/T.A. Rector & D. de Martin.

complete the Gemini North mirror coating and engineering shutdown was supported by a team of internal and external experts. Shortly after the incident, an Independent Review Board (IRB) was convened to review the incident report and the repair plans. During the initial recovery period, the internal NOIRLab team performed a detailed damage assessment and worked with the IRB to develop the detailed M1 repair plan. Concurrently, the root-cause investigation was conducted, and

the findings were addressed with improved mirror handling procedures, clarified roles and responsibilities, and strengthened oversight. The on-site mirror repair work by external contractors from Safran-REOSC and the NOIRLab repair team began in late February 2023 and was completed in April 2023. Following the completion of the repairs, the M1 stripping and coating was executed in April–May 2023, using the improved set of procedures and after providing additional managerial

support to the team. Additional work in May 2023 was required to reassemble the telescope and test its performance following the repairs. On 02 June, the Gemini North telescope returned to on-sky observations, with the primary mirror achieving its full performance and ~10% improved reflectivity following the recoating.

For more details see: [GN M1 2022 incident and repairs final report](#).

We would like to thank the Gemini/NOIRLab M1 repair team, led by NOIRLab Engineering Services Head of Optical & Mechanical Engineering Slawomir Bucki and supported by the NOIRLab Optical Engineering team and other experts within NOIRLab. On-site preparations and repair work and the engineering shutdown were led by Andrew Galvan, Andy Adamson, Steve Hardash, and Michiel van der Hoeven, with support from the cross-NOIRLab and Gemini/NOIRLab summit and engineering teams. The Independent Review Board was led by Jim Oschmann (retired, former Gemini construction project manager) and included Larry Stepp (retired), Eric Hansen (Thirty Meter Telescope), John Hill (University of Arizona), Dennis McBride (W.M. Keck Observatory), and Scott Roberts (NRC Herzberg Astronomy and Astrophysics Research Centre). External contractors from Safran-REOSC (France) provided preparatory work and on-site repair work.